

OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING SOFTWARE FOR THE “INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES” SUBJECT IN PRIMARY GRADES UNDER DIGITALIZATION CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses modern approaches to teaching the subject “Information Technologies” in primary grades in the context of rapidly developing digital technologies. In particular, it focuses on the creation and improvement of educational software that supports this subject. The author substantiates the importance of digital tools in modern educational processes and emphasizes the need for interactive, visual, functional, and intuitive software products for future primary school teachers. The article also proposes ways to increase educational effectiveness through the integration of multimedia, gamification, artificial intelligence, virtual laboratories, educational platforms and tools for collaboration and communication.*

Keywords: *digitalization, information technology, primary grades, software, multimedia tools, educational platforms.*

Phrases such as “new educational environment” and “open information space” have firmly established themselves in our daily lives. Digital technologies provide unrestricted access to a vast amount of diverse information. They are designed to facilitate the easy and fast transmission of various types of data.

In recent decades, a new component—computers and their capabilities—has been added to the traditional education paradigm of “teacher – student – textbook”. This addition has enabled the development of software based on various subjects, thereby accelerating the educational process, enhancing its visual aspects, and increasing overall effectiveness.

Practice shows that it is currently impossible to imagine a modern educational environment without new information technologies. Therefore, it is of great importance to teach future primary school teachers how to use digital technologies as tools in their professional activities. At the same time, it is equally important to develop their motivation for learning and creative potential. These tasks can be effectively addressed by creating and implementing various types of educational computer software into the learning process.

The purpose of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Informatization" is to regulate relations in the field of informatization, the use of information resources, and information systems. It also aims to organize the development of modern tools for information technologies, support the formation of markets for information resources, services and technologies, promote the development and incentivization of software products, accelerate scientific research in this field, and solve many other important issues.

In the 21st century, education is recognized globally as a key factor in ensuring sustainable development. The international education agenda set for 2030 identifies “access to quality education and fostering creative abilities” as one of its most urgent goals. In line with this, there is a focus on improving primary education subjects—the foundational stage of education—

according to modern requirements, using technologies that accelerate the learning process, and expanding pedagogical systems that foster learners' social engagement skills.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis-Parliament on January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasized the necessity of acquiring digital knowledge and modern information technologies to achieve development. He also highlighted the need to improve higher education standards based on international best practices, create electronic platforms for scientific achievements, and develop databases of both local and foreign research. According to the President, these efforts ultimately ensure the fastest path to national progress.

Information technology (IT) refers to a broad concept that encompasses the use of computers, networks, software, data storage systems, and other physical devices, infrastructures, and processes for the creation, processing, storage, protection, and exchange of electronic data.

As an academic discipline, Information Technology is an interdisciplinary field focused on the theoretical and practical aspects of designing, developing, implementing, using, and evaluating information systems and technologies. It explores methods for collecting, storing, processing, transmitting and presenting data using computer technologies and communication tools.

J. Keengwe notes that teaching the subject of Information Technology in primary school contributes to the development of students' logical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and creative skills. However, he emphasizes that the effectiveness of the subject greatly depends on how well its electronic software is developed.

During the research, scientific literature and practical observations related to the software of the Information Technology subject were analyzed. The review of sources showed that designing modern software for this subject should take into account the specific characteristics of future primary school teachers. The software should be user-friendly, visually appealing, include interactive elements, and support independent work by learners.

In the context of digitalization, designing modern software for the subject "Information Technology in Primary Grades" in accordance with current demands serves to enhance the effectiveness and interactivity of education and helps develop essential 21st-century skills in students.

The researcher thoroughly studied the current state of teaching the subject "Information Technology in Primary Grades" and analyzed the existing educational software through in-depth examination. Based on identified issues, the study proposes comprehensive ways, opportunities, and requirements for improving the teaching of this subject. Consequently, recommendations were developed regarding the design of educational software for this subject, its intended uses, relevant examples, and applicable technologies.

Designing the Content of the Subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" Is Closely Interconnected with the Content of Its Supporting Software

The content of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" is closely linked to the capabilities of the supporting software. The subject content should correspond to the functionalities offered by the software, and vice versa. The following proposals have been made to address these challenges:

The goals and tasks for improving the teaching of "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" were defined in advance. These include equipping future primary school teachers with modern multimedia tools, virtual labs and simulators, educational games (gamification), interactive textbooks and teaching aids, tools that enhance creativity, collaboration and

communication tools, artificial intelligence and machine learning, office applications, programming and web development, data analysis, information security, and more. The ultimate aim is to develop their professional competencies.

This process began with an analysis of the target audience, primarily assessing the preparedness, interests, and needs of future primary school teachers. To achieve the intended outcomes, key topics that need improvement and the requirements for those topics were identified and analyzed.

Based on the analysis, the types of modern educational software that support the improvement of this subject were identified. These include:

1. Use of multimedia tools – e.g., Microsoft PowerPoint, Canva, Gamma (AI-based design tool);
2. Use of office applications – e.g., word processors (using macros and VBA), spreadsheets (creating crosswords, diagrams);
3. Support for programming languages – e.g., Python;
4. Web application development – using Python, Visual Studio Code, JavaScript, PHP, Adobe Dreamweaver;
5. Gamification technologies – e.g., Kahoot;
6. Creation of interactive textbooks and learning aids – e.g., iSpring Page, ePublisher, CourseLab;
7. Information security tools – including data encryption software, traffic analysis tools, and malware protection;
8. Collaboration tools– such as cloud computing, file sharing tools, and project management systems;
9. AI and machine learning tools – including cloud service integration and support for mobile devices;
10. Virtual labs and simulators – enabling modeling of various processes and conducting experiments in virtual environments;
11. Integration of these tools and resources – using an educational platform proposed by the researcher that supports interaction between future primary school teachers and instructors (e.g., via forums or chat), and enables knowledge assessment and results tracking.

The Interrelationship Between the Subject Content and Its Software

When designing the subject content, it is essential to consider the functionalities of the supporting software. It is crucial to choose software that allows the implementation of all planned topics and practical tasks. Leveraging software capabilities maximally will enhance the development of course topics and contribute to accelerating the learning process.

It is advisable to use software in the learning process in a limited but strategic integrated manner. This approach involves students first mastering theoretical knowledge in depth, followed by reinforcement through hands-on tasks using the relevant software applications. Properly designed educational software will significantly support both theoretical comprehension and the development of practical skills.

The researcher's proposals for improving the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" are as follows:

1. expanding the functionality of the software by adding new tools and capabilities;

2. developing the software in an intuitive, convenient and understandable way for students with different levels of training;
3. improving the quality of software performance and reducing resource consumption for it;
4. ensuring integration between various components of the software and other systems;
5. developing tools aimed at facilitating the professional activities of the teacher, taking into account the specifics of his work.

The design of the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" proposed for future primary school teachers is a multi-stage process and provides for the following (see Table 1).

1-table

Promising ways to develop modern software for the subject "BSAT"

TYPES	PURPOSE	SAMPLES	TECHNOLOGIES
EDUCATIONAL GAMES (GAMIFICATION)	INCREASING THE PROFESSIONAL MOTIVATION AND ACTIVITY OF BBSO	USING SOFTWARE APPLICATIONS TO DEVELOP LOGICAL THINKING, MEMORY AND ATTENTION;	UNITY, SCRATCH, HTML5, JAVASCRIPT, KAHOOT, PRODIGY MATH, PYTHON (PYGAME).
INTERACTIVE TEXTBOOKS AND STUDY GUIDES	PRESENTING EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS IN AN INTERESTING AND CONVENIENT FORM, INCREASING PRESENTATION AND INTERACTIVITY	ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS WITH ANIMATION, SOUND, INTERACTIVE TASKS AND TESTS; VIRTUAL TOURS AND LABS THAT ENABLE INTERACTIVE LEARNING; APPLICATIONS FOR CREATING INTERACTIVE PRESENTATIONS AND QUIZZES	HTML5, CSS3, JAVASCRIPT, ADOBE ANIMATE, UNITY, GAME ACTIONS.
CREATIVITY TOOLS	ENCOURAGING CREATIVE THINKING, DEVELOPING THEIR IMAGINATION AND TEACHING SELF-DEVELOPMENT	DEVELOP STUDENTS' CREATIVITY BY CREATING INDEPENDENT GAME AND ANIMATION SMALL SOFTWARE PRODUCTS	SCRATCH, SNAP!, BLOCKY, HTML5, JAVASCRIPT, GRAPHIC EDITORS, AUDIO EDITORS.
ADAPTIVE LEARNING SYSTEMS	PERSONALIZING EDUCATION, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE INDIVIDUAL NEEDS AND	SELECTION OF THE LEVEL OF DIFFICULTY OF TASKS BASED ON THE CAPABILITIES OF BBSOs; SYSTEMS THAT OFFER PERSONALIZED CURRICULA AND RECOMMENDATIONS;	MACHINE LEARNING (ML), ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI), DATABASES, LEARNING

	CAPABILITIES OF BBSO	TOOLS FOR DIAGNOSING THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF BBSOS AND IDENTIFYING GAPS IN LEARNING.	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (LMS).
COLLABORATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS	DEVELOPING COOPERATION, COMMUNICATION AND TEAMWORK SKILLS	ONLINE PLATFORMS FOR COLLABORATIVE CREATION OF PROJECTS AND PRESENTATIONS; TOOLS FOR SHARING INFORMATION AND CONDUCTING VIDEO CONFERENCES; FORUMS AND CHATS FOR DISCUSSING EDUCATIONAL ISSUES.	(HTML5, CSS3, JAVASCRIPT) WEB TECHNOLOGIES, (GOOGLE WORKSPACE, MS. TEAMS) CLOUD SERVICES, (ZOOM, SKYPE), PLATFORMS.
APPLICATIONS FOR ASSESSING AND MONITORING IMPLEMENTATION	AUTOMATE KNOWLEDGE ASSESSMENT PROCESSES	ONLINE TESTS, QUIZZES AND AUTOMATIC RESULTS CHECKING TOOLS; SYSTEMS FOR COLLECTING AND ANALYZING DATA ON THE ACTIVITIES OF THE BBSO. APPLICATIONS FOR CREATING REPORTS AND DASHBOARDS FOR THE EDUCATOR.	DATABASES, WEB TECHNOLOGIES, LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (LMS), ANALYTICAL TOOLS.

The aim of the research was to improve the software of the subject “Information Technologies in Primary Schools” proposed by the researcher in order to develop the professional skills of future primary school teachers, by creating educational games, interactive textbooks and manuals, using software applications that assess and monitor mastery, using tools that develop creativity, and using collaboration and communication tools to accelerate learning. The opportunity to create these software products separately and use them by combining them into a single adaptive system was created.

“Interactive games”. Most of the proposed interactive games were developed in the environment of the Kahoot educational platform, which serves to increase the motivation and activity of future primary school teachers in this subject. In addition, they were given the opportunity to create their own animated, playful and interactive images by dragging ready-made block codes.

Platform	Description	Purpose	Examples
Kahoot	A platform for creating quizzes, games, and surveys.	To test knowledge in various subjects through gamified methods.	Students answer quiz questions and earn points for correct answers.
Prodigy Math	A platform that integrates mathematics with role-playing gameplay.	To study mathematics by completing engaging tasks.	Students solve math problems through game characters and scenarios.
Lecta	Contains over 2,500 tasks for independent	Provides engaging preparation using	Offers a large collection of educational materials,

	completion by primary school students.	gamification; individualized tasks and assessments.	allows innovative teaching services, and interactive simulators.
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The main goal here was to describe and create conditions and circumstances that would allow future primary school teachers to use game technologies in practice in the primary education system, as well as in their future professional activities. The researcher identifies the following main goals:

- to determine the level of use of game technologies in the primary education system;
- based on the analysis, to create conditions and circumstances that would allow the practical application of game technologies, the use of games and their elements as a means of learning;
- to systematize and describe the means of studying the motivation of teachers and students to use educational technologies and practices based on game elements in the primary education system.

Based on synonymous terms, as well as the definition of the term “educational technology” given by V.A. Slastenin, and also taking into account the essence of game technologies presented in numerous research works, we offer the following definition of game educational technology:

Game educational technologies are an interconnected scientifically based system of forms, methods and means of selecting, combining, developing, organizing and using certain game models, game elements, game practice in educational processes or for their subsequent use in order to solve pedagogical problems.

According to R.M. Ryan, the use of game elements (gamification) in primary educational processes creates a competitive environment for students and provides them with the opportunity to acquire knowledge through games. It also provides for the stimulation and interest of educational processes by awarding points to students for achieving various achievements by solving problems.

Interactive games, as an integral part of the software of the subject “Information Technologies in Primary Grades”, consist of elements such as achievements, points, leaderboards and create a basis for the development of skills and competencies of future primary school teachers, such as teamwork, self-development, motivation, enjoyment of educational activities, and joint problem-solving.

2. Interactive textbooks and teaching aids. The issue of creating integrative textbooks and teaching aids constitutes the content of the goals and objectives of teaching in the subject “Information Technologies in Primary Grades”. The following serve as the basis for their creation and use in educational processes:

- Development of professional skills of future primary school teachers through access to up-to-date information on the content and goals of education;
- Increasing the effectiveness of education;
- taking into account the multidimensional principles of mastering educational materials for future primary school teachers;
- taking into account the didactic principles of mastering educational materials for future primary school teachers;
- increasing the efficiency of using educational tools.

Interactive textbooks and manuals are an important component of the modern educational environment. They differ in a number of aspects, such as the format of presentation, method of interaction, level of interactivity and field of study:

- electronic textbooks and encyclopedias. These are digital analogues of traditional textbooks and manuals, supplemented with multimedia elements such as hyperlinks, interactive images, videos and tests.

3. Using multimedia capabilities in teaching the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Schools". Multimedia tools are used in teaching this subject for two purposes, namely informational (presentation) and interactive (electronic textbooks, electronic educational publications, encyclopedias, testing and monitoring programs, training programs). An informative presentation allows future primary school teachers to systematically, consistently and visually convey the theoretical content of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Schools".

4. Improving the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Schools" through web programming. Web programming is one of the most popular areas in the field of software development. Web programming is "programming for the Internet". This definition can be found on the Google page. This is a section focused on writing software and pages for www. Web programming allows you to create dynamic and interactive web pages that connect the user and the database.

5. Using the possibilities of modeling in creating software for the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Schools". Modeling (in the case of algorithm and software modeling) is a prerequisite for software quality.

6. Use of office suite applications in improving the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades": text editor, spreadsheets, presentation creation capabilities. The role of office applications in improving the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" is incomparable. They play an important role at various stages of the software development cycle, that is, they make a significant contribution to improving the quality and efficiency of education and expanding the capabilities of the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades".

7. Improve the software of the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades" through the use of computer graphics and infographics. These tools not only improve the visual presentation of information, but also help in the development and testing of software. In addition, the use of cloud technologies, databases (MBBT, SQL), computer networks and the Internet, information security, cryptography and artificial intelligence was also envisaged.

Here we find it necessary to cite the opinion of A.V. Rodionova: the scientist emphasizes the need to prioritize the system of interaction between the subject-object apparatus of the chain of topics in the context of the subject taught by the teacher, the teacher and educational materials.

According to the definition given in the pedagogical reference book, adaptive education is an educational technology based on building an individual trajectory of learners, taking into account their current knowledge, abilities, motivation and other characteristics. The reference book indicates that the characteristics of adaptive education are:

adaptation to the requirements of the teacher (simplified technology of information transmission and application);

adaptation to forms of education;

adaptation to the requirements of the educational institution in terms of parameters such as the number of hours, professional orientation, quality of teaching; openness to improvement.

The goal of improving the software of the subject “Information Technologies in Primary Grades” for future primary school teachers is determined by preparing them for effective professional activity in a modern information and educational environment, based on the requirements of the social order of society.

S.A. Stepanova defines the hardware and software in the complex of information and communication technologies in the education system, as well as the components required for the implementation of educational activities: information, technical, methodological tools and infrastructure elements, as means of improving teaching.

N.A. Borodina emphasizes that the use of computer (software) technologies in educational processes does not always lead to increased efficiency, and as a reason for this, she associates it with a misunderstanding of the features of organizing pedagogical dialogue in this environment. He notes that the theory and methodology of communication in a computer-based educational environment are still at the stage of development and require complex research.

N.V. Kuzmina emphasizes that the components of the pedagogical system consist of goals, content, methods, forms and means. From this opinion of N.V. Kuzmina, it is not difficult to understand that pedagogical systems are always open, as well as the constant change and development of information processes between them.

Sh.Kh. Pozilova emphasizes that computer programmers are engaged in the creation of educational software. In her opinion, although programmers have sufficient knowledge of software development, in many cases they are far from teaching methodology. This does not ensure that educational software fully meets the methodological requirements. Education should always and for everyone meet the requirements of the times. The current demand involves the creation of a new educational environment, the effective use of new information and innovative technologies, modern technical and software tools.

Software and the requirements for them, their role and importance in teaching the subject "Information Technologies in Primary Grades", changes to the software while maintaining its basic functionality. The importance of software is that it constitutes a continuous process from its creation to its use.

In general, if future primary school teachers have in their minds programmatic models and clear goals to which they aspire, then it will be easier for them to think and express themselves. For example, G.B. Skok presents the following general indicative table for conducting a pedagogical analysis that determines the actions of future primary school teachers in accordance with modern trends in the development of education (see Table 2).

2-table

Modern Trends in the Development of the Education System According to G.B. Skok

traditional approach	INNOVATIVE APPROACH
transferring knowledge and experience to the new generation	FOCUS ON INDIVIDUAL DEVELOPMENT, FORMATION, AND PROFESSIONAL GROWTH OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS (FPSTs)

preparing fpsts for future professional activity	PREPARING FPSTs FOR REAL-LIFE CHALLENGES “HERE AND NOW” WITHOUT CAUSING INCONVENIENCE TO OTHERS
preparing for a future better than current conditions	SHAPING INNOVATIVE NEEDS IN CONSTANTLY CHANGING PRESENT CONDITIONS
focus on the amount of knowledge acquired	EMPHASIS ON THE STRUCTURE AND ORGANIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE
teaching aimed at knowledge acquisition	TEACHING AIMED AT SELF-DEVELOPMENT AND ADOPTION OF MODERN METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES
learning predetermined knowledge	LEARNING THROUGH CRITICAL THINKING AND CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS
directing general, personal, and professional knowledge toward future use	APPLICATION OF GENERAL KNOWLEDGE THROUGH PROFESSIONAL SIMULATION AND PRACTICAL TASKS
reliance on repetition-based teaching	DISCOVERY OF NEW KNOWLEDGE AND PRODUCTIVE METHODS OF ACTION
knowledge disconnected from real-life challenges	ORIENTATION TOWARD SOLVING ACTUAL SOCIETAL AND HUMAN PROBLEMS
fpsts accepting pre-defined goals	ABILITY TO DEFINE, SHAPE, AND PURSUE INDIVIDUAL GOALS
fpsts avoiding assessments when possible	MOTIVATION FOR TIMELY AND OBJECTIVE ASSESSMENT
uniformity across educational institutions	RECOGNITION OF EACH INSTITUTION’S UNIQUENESS
rigid adherence to national educational standards	FLEXIBILITY AND ADAPTABILITY IN PROGRAM DESIGN
No option for FPSTs to choose their instructor	POSSIBILITY FOR FPSTs TO SELECT THEIR INSTRUCTOR
Innovations implemented once, based on authority recommendations	CONTINUOUS INNOVATION BASED ON PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS, WITH SYSTEM-WIDE IMPACT

When it comes to the use of modern educational technologies, the following possible forms of implementing information and communication technologies in the higher education system are considered:

- distance learning;
- online learning;
- use of educational platforms;
- interactive simulators, tests, surveys, etc.

Here, distance learning is understood as learning through individual use of independently developed projects.

Online education is carried out by a teacher through the creation of an information and educational environment. This form of education differs from traditional education only in the presence of a virtual environment.

Educational platforms provide for the widespread use of resources and various hardware tools necessary for the productive activities of future primary school teachers.

An educational platform is an Internet resource that contains a bank of educational content that is provided to the user under certain conditions.

The purpose of using these platforms is to provide high-quality education based on digital technologies.

In the context of digitalization, improving the software of the subject “Information Technologies in Primary Schools” opens up wide opportunities for future primary school teachers. From software tools to machine learning, as well as cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, the use of mobile devices, etc., open up new horizons for creating innovative software solutions that meet the needs of digital education. Software is not just a tool, but a key factor in competitiveness, efficiency and innovation in any field.

CONCLUSION: The article emphasizes that in the traditional education system, instead of the “teacher - student - textbook”, the “teacher - students - digital resources” system is gaining a strong place. In particular, in the training of primary school teachers, it is possible to increase their pedagogical effectiveness by teaching them information and communication technologies (ICT) as an active means of educational and professional activity. Information technologies play an important role not only in visually enriching lessons, but also in developing independent thinking, creative approaches and problem-solving skills.

The study pays special attention to the close relationship between subject content and software. Software should be designed not only to provide theoretical knowledge in the educational process, but also to perform practical tasks in preparing students for professional activity. Therefore, technological solutions that cover each subject of the subject, serve to explain and strengthen it - presentations, interactive textbooks, web applications, modern platforms such as Python, Scratch, Kahoot, Canva, iSpring, CourseLab - are recommended. The article emphasizes the need to ensure the participation of not only programmers, but also pedagogical methodologists in the development of educational software. After all, in many cases, although software products are technically well-designed, they do not sufficiently take into account pedagogical content and didactic requirements. Therefore, it is urgent to develop scientifically based, adaptive, multi-stage, student-centered programs, integrating the capabilities of modern educational technologies - distance, online, platform-based education, simulators, information security, artificial intelligence and mobile applications.

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